

1 **HPV E2 activates ESF1.**

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6 HPV E2 is the viral transcriptional activator but likely has a multitude of functions separate from the
7 E1-associated viral trans-activation event that remain undefined. We demonstrate here by ectopic
8 expression of HPV E2 in human cells and measurement of total transcription following next generation
9 RNA-sequencing activation of *Esf1* by human papillomavirus E2 protein.

10 Citations

11 1. Peng, W.T., Krogan, N.J., Richards, D.P., Greenblatt, J.F. and Hughes, T.R., 2004. ESF1 is
12 required for 18S rRNA synthesis in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Nucleic acids research*, 32(6),
13 pp.1993-1999.

14 GSE121627